

HISTORICAL NOVELS AND CHARACTER SPEECH: LANGUAGE, STYLE, AND EXPRESSION OF THE SPIRIT OF THE ERA

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Abstract

This article analyzes the linguistic and artistic features of character speech in historical novels, as well as its role in conveying the spirit of the era. Using examples from the novel “O‘tkan kunlar” (“Bygone Days”), the study highlights issues such as achieving historicity through character speech, revealing the traits of protagonists, and reflecting the socio-cultural environment.

Keywords: character speech, dialogue, monologue, spirit of the era, historical truth, national spirit, artistic texture, language individuality, pronunciation norms.

Each historical period has its own distinct style of speech. In historical novels, this is undoubtedly one of the crucial elements. In this regard, during the translation process, it is of great importance to accurately convey the unique characteristics of the characters’ speech and language. This helps the reader form a correct understanding of the historical period. The individual features of historical characters’ speech are closely linked to their social status, profession, and position within their society. For example, the language of palace officials or members of the nobility should differ from that of ordinary people. Such distinctions play a significant role in historical novels.

At this point, it is also necessary to clarify questions such as what a literary character is and for what purposes the author employs them. A character is an individual depicted by the author in art and literature. Depending on their participation, depiction, and level of generalization within the work, characters are classified as main, supporting, or episodic [1]. Characters who actively participate in the events from the beginning to the end of the literary work and convey the author’s primary ideological-aesthetic intent are considered main characters. These include the protagonists of the story. Those who do not fully participate in all events but help reveal the author’s ideas more fully are supporting characters. Characters who appear less frequently in the macrostructure of the work are considered episodic; they serve to convincingly highlight important traits of the main characters.

Depending on the author's attitude, characters are depicted as either positive or negative. In a literary work, such contrasting characters reflect the eternal literary problem of life, which consists of both good and evil. Through

characters, life events are expressed at various levels. In particular, in historical works, events are conveyed through the characters, and their speech also acquaints the reader with history. For this reason, historical novels are one of the important genres of literature, serving as a means to depict past events and significant societal changes. The uniqueness of characters' speech is one of the distinctive features of this genre.

At this point, it is appropriate to discuss the types of speech in literary works. In literature, types of speech are a set of linguistic units and stylistic devices used by the author to convey artistic reality, reveal the character of the hero, and show the author's attitude. In literary theory, they are mainly divided into two types:

1. Author's speech. This is the type of speech in which the author himself narrates the events of the work.

2. Character speech. Character speech appears in the form of dialogue and monologue. Dialogue is a type of speech based on the interactions between characters. Dialogue gives the work liveliness and naturalness. The character's personality is revealed through their dialogue, and it is effective in advancing the plot. Monologue is a longer, continuous speech of the character, in which their inner experiences, thoughts, and emotional states are deeply revealed. It can be an internal reflection, a thought, or a long address to other characters.

In literary works, each character's speech is directly related to their gender, age, social status, and occupation. Through this, the author vividly reveals the character's personality.

In historical novels, the meaning is mainly conveyed through the speech of the characters, as we can observe through examples. In historical works, the speech of characters is of great importance. Through it, the spirit of the era, social relations, and the inner experiences of the characters are expressed. In the novel *O'tkan kunlar*, the speech of characters allows a deeper understanding of the social and political environment, customs, and interpersonal relationships of the historical period. At this point, we can outline the main functions of characters' speech as follows:

- Reflecting the spirit of the era – through characters' speech, the language, style, and culture of that period are revealed;
- Revealing the characters' personality – this function shows the characters' traits through their way of speaking, expressions, and unique features of their speech;

- Depicting social relations – dialogues between characters depict social relationships and conflicts within society.

The uniqueness of the novel “O’tkan kunlar” (“Bygone days”) is manifested in its theme, characters, language and style, as well as in the harmony of historical reality and artistic texture. The characters in the novel represent various social strata, and their personalities are distinctive and colorful. For example, Otabek is portrayed as a patriotic, brave, and justice-loving young man, Kumush as a loyal, kind, and beautiful girl, while Homid is depicted as cunning, selfish, and treacherous. The author extensively uses expressions peculiar to the vernacular, proverbs, and examples of oral folk creativity. This method enhances the artistic value of the work and helps the reader deeply feel the atmosphere of that period. It combines historical events with artistic texture, providing the reader with a truthful understanding of the past. In this regard, the emphasis of T. Dostnazarov in his scholarly article “Abdulla Qodiriy’s novel “O’tgan kunlar” narrates our history during the “Khan periods” that “in Abdulla Qodiriy’s works, the national spirit and folklore traditions are harmonized, revealing the author’s unique and unparalleled style” [2] is also a clear confirmation of our point. In the novel, Kumush’s courage is depicted in the pages where she goes fearlessly to the governor of Marg’ilon to save her father along with her husband from the clutches of death. These scenes portray not only her bravery but also her bold speech and readiness to face even death in pursuit of the truth.

“- Maktub qayerda ekan?

- Uning eski kamzulinig cho’ntagida ekan.

Shu gapdan keyin qushbegi maktubni o’ziga yaqin o’lturg’an Azim ponsadboshig’a uzatdi:

- Siz ham o’qub ko’ringchi, ponsad, - dedi va Kumushdan so’radi:

- O’qug’anmisiz?

- O’qug’anman.

- Eringizning hukumatka qarshi harakatini ilgari ham bilar edingizmi?

- Qanaqa harakatini?

- Masalan, biz otangiz bilan eringizni nima uchun osmoqchi bo’ldiq?

- Haqsiz, gunohsiz! [3].

In the sample text provided, along with historical accuracy, examples of speech patterns typical of that era appear in the characters’ dialogue, such as “ponsadboshig’a,” “o’qug’anmisiz,” “hukumatka,” and “bo’ldiq”. In the translation of historical works, translating such words accurately is of great importance and requires careful attention. In this regard, the following remarks by translation

scholar G.Salomov serve as clear evidence: “Determining the linguistic individuality of characters is an important issue not only in the original literature but also in literary translation. Indeed, a translator working with classic literary works is obliged to convey the vocabulary and pronunciation norms specific to the era in which the characters’ speech is set” [4].

As we emphasized above, the author is able to depict very delicate situations in a highly vivid and expressive manner. Even today, the novel continues to be passionately discussed by readers. Upon hearing the title of the work, readers immediately imagine Otabek and Kumush, and the pure love between them comes to life in their minds. This also testifies to the author’s high level of expressive skill. At the same time, the depiction of other characters in the work is also presented in a distinctive manner. For example, in the pages describing Homid’s plot against Otabek, his cunning, selfishness, and evil intentions are revealed. Through these pages, the author teaches the reader a lesson about the consequences of wrongdoing. We can see this clearly in the following example:

“Qo’rboshi tokchadan davot (siyohdon), qalam olib oldig’a qo’ydi-da, yozuvig’a hozirlanib so’radi:

- Ayt-chi, Homidboy, muttahamlar kim edi?
- Bittasi toshkandlik Yusufbek hojining o’g’li – Otabek.

Qo’rboshi yozdi:

- Ha-ha! Hali Yusufbek hojining o’g’li degin. Bizning Marg’ilonni ham qong’a botirmoqchi ekanda, muttahamlar, ikkinchisi?
- Shu kunlarda Otabekka qizini bergan marg’ilonlik Mirzakarim.
- Pes-pesni qorong’ida topqan ekan, uchinchisi?
- Otabekning quli – Hasanali.
- To’rtinchisi?

Homid biroz o’ylanib javob berdi:

- Bilmadim ... Hozir Marg’ilondami, yo’qmi, Andijonlik Akram hoji” [5].

Here, the author exposes the true of nature of envy and people who commit evil for their own benefit. Through the speech of the characters, readers perceive scenes that evoke a sense of disgust toward such elements in society and ultimately encourage people to remain free from these vices. As the events of the story unfold, we witness envious and slanderous individuals experiencing shame. This also emphasizes once again that lies have a short life.

In conclusion. It can be stated that in historical novels, the speech of the characters is one of the main artistic tools of the work, playing a crucial role in

conveying the spirit of the historical period, social relations, and the inner experiences of the protagonists. Every era has its own distinctive style of speech, and preserving this style in translation enhances the historical and artistic value of the work. The individual speech of characters is closely linked to their social status, occupation, gender, and age, and it vividly reveals the personality of each character.

Using “O’tkan kunlar” (“Bygone days”) as an example, it can be seen that through the characters’ speech patterns, expressions, and elements of folk oral creativity, the reader experiences the atmosphere of that period more deeply. Otabek’s patriotism, Kumush’s courage, and honid’s selfishness are clearly expressed through character speech. At the same time, the dialogue between characters reveals social conflicts and life situations, helping the reader develop moral and ethical understanding.

Thus, in historical novels, character speech serves not only to reveal personality but also as a primary means to convey the past, customs, and social relations to the reader. Preserving the historical and linguistic features of this speech in translations is essential to fully reflect the essence of the work

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